

Market opportunities for Microfinance Institutions

Abstract

Taking a business scholar's standpoint I assess the future of the microfinance industry. The basic question I try to answer is why the microfinance market continues to grow while public support for the industry is shrinking. I identify six underlying forces - demographic transition; reduced poverty; urbanisation; economic growth; technological innovations; and shifts in microfinance paradigms – that drive the growth of the microfinance industry. Furthermore, I identify six non-traditional microfinance markets that may represent interesting opportunities in the years to come: insurance, housing, small and medium enterprise lending, savings, micropensions, and microfinance in high-income countries. I conclude the article highlighting that policy makers, regulators and international support organizations may encourage or hamper the future as outlined in this article.

Key words: Growth drivers; market opportunities; future; housing; micropensions

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Section 1: Introduction

Why does the microfinance market continue to grow while public support for the industry is shrinking? In this article, I highlight the underlying forces that are driving growth in the microfinance sector. Additionally, I analyse market trends that will promote continued growth in the years to come. Although much of the microfinance debate focuses on ‘impact and development’, my primary argument is that basic market forces will drive the future of the industry. Thus, in the rest of this article, which is a modified summary of the plenary speech that I gave at the 3rd European Research Conference on Microfinance, held at the University of Agder in Kristiansand, Norway, on June 10-12, 2013, I study the microfinance market from a business scholar’s standpoint. Moreover, I use the term Microfinance Institution (MFI) to signal a market oriented provider of banking services to low-income families and micro-enterprises. I recognize that the view of a business scholar may be narrow and that many providers of microfinance services may not consider themselves market oriented. Nevertheless, when discussing the future of microfinance, I consider a better understanding of market forces important.

In recent years, the microfinance industry has experienced several setbacks. The Wall Street Journal and several other outlets have reported tragic suicides among microborrowers in the Indian state of Andhra Pradesh, and Banco Compartamos continues to sell overpriced loans to poor customers in Mexico. Duvendack et al. (2011) report that when researchers apply rigorous methodology, they generally struggle to identify strong evidence that microborrowing actually provides a way out of poverty. Given this situation, one might think that demand for microfinance would fall and the supply of microfinance services would shrink. Instead, the microfinance market continues to grow. Mersland and Strøm (2013) report that the global microfinance industry has had annual growth rates of between 40 and 60 per cent over the last 10 years.

Take, for instance, the case of Bolivia, a country recognised as a leader in the microfinance industry. In the 1990s, after Bolivia had operated microfinance operations for a decade, Gonzalez-Vega et al. (1997) assessed that country’s success by conducting a survey of its best microfinance organisations and their clients. They concluded that the market was saturated and that future microcredit growth was unlikely. However, since then the size of the Bolivian market has multiplied several times. In fact, one of the microfinance organisations that was

studied, Banco FIE, demonstrates that growth. Since its start up in 1988, the bank’s portfolio has increased every year and now totals \$765 million in US dollars (Graph 1).

Note: FIE started out as an NGO and did not take deposits until 1998, when it became a bank.
 Source: Direct communication from Banco FIE, Bolivia.

Banco FIE is not the exception. Several MFIs have experienced strong growth over several years. How can this be possible? Motivated to answer this question, this paper explores the disconnect between public support for microfinance and market reality. The rest of this paper is organised as follows: In section 2, I present what I believe are the forces driving the observed growth in the microfinance sector. In section 3, I present microfinance segments in which continued growth can be expected. Section 4 concludes the article.

Section 2: Underlying forces driving the growth of microfinance

In my opinion, there are six main, underlying market forces that have supported the growth in microfinance in recent years and will continue to drive growth in the future. These six forces are as follows: demographic transition, reduced poverty, urbanisation, economic growth, technological innovations and shifts in microfinance paradigms. Below, I describe these forces in more detail.

1. Demographic transition

This phenomenon is an obvious but often-forgotten reason for market growth. The United Nations (2013a) has estimated that the population of the least developed countries (LDCs) will double by mid-century, making that population the fastest growing in the world, at a rate of 2.3 per cent per year. The LDCs' markets are the most appropriate for microfinance services. In addition, the world's population pyramids are shifting rapidly. With relatively fewer children, a larger share of the population will be of working age, between 18 and 70 years old (www.populationpyramid.net/). For instance, in 2010, 40 per cent of Peru's 29 million inhabitants were under the age of 20; by 2050, only 24 per cent of its estimated 39 million people will be that age. Similarly, Uganda's population is expected to increase from 33 million to 94 million inhabitants between 2010 and 2050, whereas it is estimated that the proportion of its population under the age of 20 will decrease from 60 per cent to approximately 45 per cent. These considerable shifts in world demographics, not only in the number of people but also in the share of the population that is of working age, is greatly influencing the demand for microfinance services (Graph 2). MFIs grow simply because there are more potential customers in the market.

Graph 2.

Larger populations drive the demand for financial services

2. Reduced poverty

The reduction in poverty in the World is encouraging (Graph 3). According to the latest Human Development Report (United Nations, 2013b:13), “The first Millennium Development Goal of halving the proportion of people living on less than \$1.25 a day relative to 1990 has been met three years before the target date”. This reduction in poverty is a global phenomenon, with populous countries such as Brazil, China and India at the forefront (United Nations, 2013b). When people are less poor, their demand for financial services naturally increases. This reduction in poverty is a major force in determining the size of the microfinance market. Less poverty results in increased cash flows and thus an increased demand for savings. Moreover, reduced poverty permits MFIs to make larger loans.

Graph 3.

Reduced poverty drives demand for financial services

3. Urbanisation

In 2008, for the first time in history, more than half of the world’s population was living in urban areas, and by 2050, it is estimated that 7 out of 10 people will live in urban areas (WHO, 2010). Compared to rural areas, people living in urban areas have generally higher cash flows and a greater need for financial services. In addition, cash flow management involving bank services is more necessary in urban areas than in rural areas, where stocked grains, livestock and agricultural products are more easily available. In particular, payment

services are in high demand by urban dwellers who need to pay their electricity bills, receive their salaries or cash in their remittances or public pensions.

4. Economic growth

Economic growth facilitates MFI growth. Historically, economic growth has been driven by the OECD economies; however, in the future, growth will likely be driven by emerging markets. Although economic growth in OECD countries has been between 1 and 2 per cent in recent years, growth in emerging markets and developing economies is expected to remain robust at approximately 5 per cent (Helbling, 2013). This observation means that economic growth is now much higher in countries where microfinance is widely practiced compared to countries where traditional banking dominates. As a result, the main microfinance markets in emerging economies are expected to experience high growth. Stronger economies generate more business opportunities, allowing MFIs to grow with their customers and expand their businesses.

5. Innovations and technology open up new markets

In recent years, mobile phone technology and coverage has experienced explosive development and increased capacity. The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) estimates that there are more than 6 billion mobile phone subscriptions worldwide and that 79 per cent of people in emerging economies have access to a mobile phone (ITU, 2011). In Africa, there are more than 500 million mobile phone users (Rao, 2011). The spread of mobile phone technology may now gradually enable people who have never had a bank account, or who live far away from a bank office, to access basic financial services (United Nations, 2013b). For instance, after a few years of operation, the M-Pesa money transfer service operated in partnership between Vodaphone and Equity Bank in Kenya has reached 14 million users. Moreover, the boundaries between the banking and telecommunications industries are blurring. An example of this blurring is international telecommunications giant Telenor's recent takeover of Tameer Microfinance Bank, the largest microfinance bank in Pakistan. According to Mersland and Thøgersen (forthcoming), "The future of banking lies in telecom, and much future telecom business will be related to banking".

6. Shifts in microfinance paradigms

Microfinance is an industry that has many paradigms. For instance, the stereotype of microfinance services is that they are equivalent to a short-term, group-guaranteed loan that

increases the working capital of a self-employed woman in her forties. In fact, D'Espallier et al. (2011) report that 3 out of 4 microfinance customers are women and 40 per cent of MFIs consciously focus on women (i.e., they prefer female customers). This focus hinders MFIs' growth and sustainability. Increasingly, MFIs acknowledge that excluding men reduces their market potential. D'Espallier et al. (2013) report that even though MFIs that focus on women have better repayment rates, their overall profitability is on par with MFIs that focus equally on men and women. The reason for this is that women take smaller loans which are less profitable for MFIs and which equals out the benefit from better repayment by female customers. Thus, shifting the paradigm away from a solely female focus will result in a huge increase in the microfinance market.

In addition to gender, other on-going paradigm shifts that are likely to affect growth in the microfinance market include the following facts: 1) MFIs are shifting to individual lending instead of group lending, allowing for larger loan amounts (i.e., increased MFI portfolios) (Mersland and Strøm, 2012); 2) Recently, the trend among MFIs has been to shift from a singular focus on working capital loans to servicing their customers with many types of loans. Market-oriented MFIs are increasingly offering loan products to finance assets, housing, consumption, education and health; 3) For many years, CGAP and other institutions have advocated for a shift from microcredit to servicing poor people with many types of financial services, such as savings, insurance, money transfers and payment facilities (CGAP, 2013); 4) As funding grows and repayment rates are controlled, MFIs will serve their customers with longer-term loans. MFI managers focusing on sustainability understand that by increasing loan terms from 12 to 18 months, their portfolios and income increase by 50 per cent while their operating costs, at least in theory, remain unchanged; 5) Another important change is the shift from serving only self-employed customers to serving any customer who has the capacity to repay. In particular, it can be expected that a larger number of salaried workers will become customers of MFIs; 6) Likewise, MFIs can increase their customer base and their portfolios by gradually shifting their focus from customers aged 25-55 to younger and older customers; and finally, 7) More MFIs, such as Banco FIE, have shifted from focusing only on microenterprises to increasingly focus on small- and medium-sized enterprises that have a demand for more professionalised and advanced MFI services, including higher capital needs.

Most of the aforementioned paradigm shifts are already taking place in professionalised MFIs operating in competitive markets (e.g., Bolivia). The main “think tanks”, such as CGAP, are well aware of these shifts (CGAP, 2013). Additionally, there are thousands of “socially responsible” investors who have turned their eyes to the microfinance sector. The groundbreaking book “The fortune at the Bottom of the Pyramid: Eradicating Poverty Through Profits”, by the late Michigan professor C.K. Prahalad, advocates microfinance as a good business case for investors interested in “doing good by doing well”. This inflow of capital, interest, and knowledge will continue to drive innovations and expand the microfinance market in the years to come.

Section 3: Future potential markets for Microfinance

In addition to the six forces driving the general growth in the microfinance industry, there are non-traditional microfinance markets that will, I believe, experience sustainable growth in the future and allow the microfinance sector to become the world’s largest banking market in terms of number of customers. However, before going into detail about these market opportunities, I would like to note two reasons that there is also still a considerable unexploited demand for traditional microcredit services: the need for smooth cash flows and the need to finance self-employment activities. Rutherford (2000) described better than anyone else how the poor must manage unstable cash flows. With an unstable cash flow comes the need for financial services from MFIs, such as savings accounts, or, during harsh times, the need and volition to borrow money to cover unexpected expenses. In addition, formal labour sectors are not growing sufficiently to allow poor people to acquire stable incomes from salaried jobs. Accordingly, people will continue to be pushed into what is known in the literature as “necessity entrepreneurial activities” (Acs, 2006), which demand capital to operate. Thus, demand for microcredit will remain high.

Following are six non-traditional microfinance markets that may represent interesting opportunities in the years to come: insurance, housing, small and medium enterprise lending, savings, micropensions, and microfinance in high-income countries.

1. Insurance

Microfinance practitioners have long known of microinsurance, but the service is still not considered to be a mainstream microfinance service. Insurance policies are often compulsorily attached to loan contracts to increase the MFI’s effective interest rates, and in so

doing, cover the real cost of microlending (www.mftransparency.org). Likewise, the types of policies offered often cover the need of the lender (credit insurance, life insurance, etc.) rather than the need of the policyholder. As a result, insurance is not a typical MFI service, and target customers have often been reluctant to voluntarily contract for insurance policies. In fact, the world's leading specialist in insurance markets, Lloyd's, estimates that between one point five and three billion people in low-income countries are underserved by insurance (Lloyd's, 2012). However, they claim there is a strong demand for health and life insurance, agricultural insurance, property insurance and catastrophe coverage. According to Craig Churchill, Chair of the Microinsurance Network and Head of the ILO's Microinsurance Innovation Facility, there are 500 million people in low-income countries who already have some type of microinsurance, but it is estimated that within 10 years, the market could grow to 1 billion microinsurance policy holders (Lloyd's, 2012).

Two important conditions will enable the foreseen growth in microinsurance markets: first, the use of new technologies to reduce costs related to frequent and small transactions; and second, innovative delivery channels that will allow any institution with access to low-income households to become an insurance agent (Lloyd's, 2012). In this view, MFIs, which have millions of clients and branch networks, are attractive partners for insurance companies. As previously mentioned, several MFIs offer microinsurance services combined with loans and occasionally with savings accounts, but such insurance products are usually mandatory. The next step for MFIs is to be able to offer voluntary insurance products not attached to their own credit or savings products.

2. Housing

Close to one billion people live in slum conditions, usually in overcrowded, poorly constructed housing (WHO, 2010). With the demographic transition towards urban areas and a growing demand for small, high-quality household units, the future market for housing finance is enormous. According to Cohen (2005), by 2050, there will be 2.6 billion new urban residents in cities in low-income countries. Mortgage finance constitutes less than 10 per cent of GDP in most low-income countries, compared to 42 per cent and 79 per cent in the European Union and the US, respectively (Ferguson and Smets, 2010). This contrast illustrates the potential for growth in housing microfinance. However, the challenges of tapping the microfinance housing market are many and include weak property rights, unclear national housing subsidy regimes, lack of long-term funding for MFIs, and customers'

unstable incomes, which make long-term loans risky. Nevertheless, faced with an enormous unmet demand combined with increased competition in traditional microcredit, I am certain that many MFIs will find ways to service this market. Currently, many MFIs offer to finance housing, primarily in the form of short-term home improvement loans. Such loans, whether they are for salaried workers or self-employed people, are well tailored to demand because “incremental building accounts for 50-90% of residential development in most developing-country cities” (Ferguson and Smets, 2010:288). Gradually, as risk management in MFIs improves and longer-term funding becomes available, we can also expect that MFIs will offer traditional mortgage loans for the purchase of new and used houses. Also worth noticing, especially for those who are concerned about the social impact of microfinance, is the importance that poor people attach to their housing conditions and the significant contribution of the construction industry to the economic growth of low-income countries (Giang and Pheng, 2011). Thus, MFIs interested in pursuing double bottom line should indeed be interested in increasing their housing loan portfolios in the future.

3. Capital for small and medium enterprises

As previously mentioned, traditional microcredit has been primarily targeted to what is known in the entrepreneurship literature as “necessity entrepreneurship”. These are self-employment initiatives by individuals who have no other formal employment options. This type of entrepreneurship normally generates small profits for the owner and contributes little, or even negatively, to economic growth (Acs, 2006). People will continue to use microcredit for these types of ventures as long as “there are substantial bureaucratic barriers to formally creating a new business, or simply that the economy is creating too few conventional wage-earning job opportunities” (Asc, 2006:97). Although the economies of emerging market countries are changing rapidly and becoming more suitable for formal industries, there is still a vast need for capital to invest in necessity entrepreneurship ventures.

However, in the future, we can expect a higher demand for capital by small and medium enterprises (SME) operating in emerging economies. Although SMEs contribute on average 49 per cent of national GDP in high-income countries, their contribution is only 29 per cent on average in low-income countries (Ayyagari et al., 2007). This low contribution is the result of difficulties for small firms to access markets, lack of infrastructure, bureaucratic regulations etc., but it is also a result of relatively few loans given to small and medium enterprises. While the median ratio of loans in relation to GDP given to SMEs is 13 per cent

in high-income countries it is only 3 per cent in low-income countries. Consequently, 70 per cent of all SME lending is concentrated in OECD countries (CGAP/World Bank, 2010). According to the World Bank, lack of access to loans consistently ranks as a major obstacle to doing business, and although 56 per cent of large firms report having a loan, only 32 per cent of SMEs report having one (CGAP/World Bank, 2010). In addition, the extent of loan accounts in a country is clearly associated with its GDP and level of banking competition. Thus, people living in low-income countries and in countries with less banking competition have less access to credit.

To date, MFIs have been rated “better” when they have serviced poorer customers with smaller loans (Mersland and Strøm, 2010). In this regard, the strategy shift by Procredit, one of the most important international microfinance holding companies, and which has operations in 21 countries around the world, is interesting. A few years ago, Procredit decided to shift away from the micro-micro segment to focus on lending to SMEs (www.procredit-holding.com). Those who believe that MFIs should focus on reaching the “poorest of the poor” may criticise Procredit, but to preserve Procredit’s sustainability and for low-income countries’ economic growth, this decision may prove to be more successful than the traditional MFI market strategy focusing on the poorest customers.

4. Savings

Savings are regarded as the missing half of microfinance. If microfinance is ‘banking’ for the poor, then microfinance is about the intermediation of local resources. Nevertheless, because of regulatory issues, and because modern microfinance began as a lending movement, most MFIs do not take deposits. The seminal work of Rutherford (2000), together with important initiatives by CGAP, the Gates Foundation and several others, has placed savings on the microfinance agenda. Although several hundred million poor individuals have already a savings account, the untapped savings market is still huge. According to CGAP/World Bank (2010), the rate of banked households (i.e., households that have at least one deposit account in a formal financial institution) is 91 per cent in OECD countries but only 40 per cent in Latin America, 22 per cent in South Asia and 12 per cent in Africa. Obviously, if participation in informal banking systems like Rotating Savings and Credit Associations (ROSCAs) and Village Savings and Loan Associations (VSLAs) was included, it would become clear that many more low-income families save regularly (Rutherford, 2000). There is thus a market for MFIs interested in ‘microsavings’.

Urbanisation together with new technologies will drive the growth in microsavings in the years to come. For instance, the largest microfinance bank in Kenya, Equity Bank, has over 7.8 million accounts, which represent 50 per cent of all savings accounts in the country. This bank owes its success to new technological innovations coupled with new banking agents. With the help of mobile phone technology (M-Kesho), users can deposit or withdraw small amounts of money in almost every small kiosk or shop in the country. Equity Bank reports that mobile banking customers increased from 417,000 to 1.8 million from January 2011 to June 2012 (www.equitybank.co.ke – investor presentation second semester 2012).

There have been two main barriers to microsavings: how to regulate appropriately and how to control the cost of mobilising savings. Despite these barriers, several MFIs now use local savings to finance important parts of their portfolios. Banco FIE, for instance, finances approximately 80 per cent of its portfolio with local savings. Hopefully, in the future, savings will become the largest microfinance service, and customers will be newborn babies, teenagers, students, working-age individuals and pensioners.

5. Pension schemes

As previously mentioned, the world's population is experiencing a dramatic transition in demographics. The population pyramids of high-income countries have already changed from the traditional pyramids to standing rectangles with a small triangle on top. In countries such as Peru and Morocco, there are fewer young children than there are teenagers. In Bangladesh, life expectancy has increased by 20 years since 1980. By 2050, it is estimated that 80 per cent of the 2 billion elderly worldwide will be living in low-income countries, where one in five people will be over 60 years of age (Shetty, 2012). Even in Africa, where fertility rates are still high, it is expected that the number of people over 60 years of age will triple to 150 million by 2050 (Shetty, 2012). The health threat related to an ageing population in low-income countries is now finally on the agenda of organisations such as the World Health Organisation and the UN (Shetty, 2012). Even in light of these projections, few discuss what the demographic transition will mean in terms of demand for financial services and, in particular, pensions.

The development magazine *Udvikling*, issued by the Danish foreign ministry DANIDA, recently published an article titled “The breakup of Africa's big families”. This article not only draws attention to the challenge that low-income countries face as a result of a larger

number of elderly but also underscores the cultural and urbanisation-related changes that will increase the demand for pensions, savings and other financial services targeting elderly people. For instance, parents can no longer expect that their children will take care of them in old age because often, their children have migrated to other cities and have their own families to take care of. Studies have shown (e.g., Aborderin (2004) in Ghana) that resource constraints and the expectation of self-reliance in old age result in less cross-generational support.

Consequently, the elderly living in low-income countries will have to face old age as the elderly do in high-income countries: relying on government and/or private pensions and personal savings. Sadly, less than 25 per cent of elderly in middle- and low-income countries have access to social security support (Holzmann et al., 2009). Accordingly, there is a great need for new micropension initiatives. In addition, working-age people in low-income countries are not used to thinking about how to protect their livelihood in their old age. Some low-income countries have designed new policies, but few people can expect that their governments will be able to finance much of their living costs in old age. Few micropension initiatives driven by MFIs have been created, but the Pension & Development Network disseminates information about the current and future need for old-age financial services (www.pensiondevelopment.org).

6. Microfinance in high-income countries

The recent economic crisis, together with high levels of immigration from low-income countries, has given rise to an emerging microfinance market in high-income countries, particularly in Southern Europe and the US. Even before the crisis, a 2007 European Union survey showed that 7 per cent of individuals in the EU believed that it was difficult to access a bank account, and 2 per cent of households did not have a bank account at all (European Commission, 2009). A more recent study found that 8 per cent of adult Italians do not have access to a bank account (European Commission, 2009). Thus, we can expect that financial inclusion (i.e., microfinance) will become a relevant policy issue in Europe in the coming years. Currently, the European Microfinance Network, supported by the European Union, has 93 members that work to promote microfinance activities across Europe. The EU has also introduced packages to provide small entrepreneurs with microcredit and is stimulating banks to increase their microcredit services (European Commission, 2010).

Moreover, microfinance is now high on the agenda in the US, and several institutions, such as Accion International, are actively providing financial services to unemployed and poor individuals (Richardson, 2009). The focus in the US has not only been on credit but also on facilitating Individual Development Accounts (IDA), which are savings accounts in which governments or other institutions match the depositor's personal efforts. Often the match rate is 1:1, so that \$100 saved by the depositor results in a \$200 deposit into the savings account (Schreiner and Sherraden, 2007). Such matching initiatives are interesting and could also serve as inspiration for MFIs in low-income countries, although to date, we have observed few such initiatives by traditional MFIs and their donors.

In EU countries, governments are struggling to continue to finance generous welfare schemes and as a result, such schemes have been reduced or eliminated, particularly in Southern European countries. In the years to come, I foresee that an increasing number of politicians will seek to replace welfare programs for the unemployed with support for self-employment initiatives. Thus, microfinance may soon find fertile ground in the EU and most likely in the US as well.

Section 4: Conclusions

In this paper, I do not focus on development but instead use a traditional business-school perspective to discuss the future of the microfinance industry. Like it or not, traditional market forces are gradually taking over the industry. MFIs no longer operate in monopoly conditions and they increasingly need to adopt traditional market strategies to remain competitive. In this regard, today's MFIs are similar to 19th-century savings banks, which gradually became pragmatic bank organisations in order to survive and provide relevant services to their customers (Mersland, 2011).

Even though public support for microfinance has diminished in recent years, we can expect continued growth in the microfinance sector as the result of important forces that are driving the markets. In such a market scenario, rigorous academic research on the operation and efficiency of MFIs is needed. For instance, if the industry is plagued by high operating costs, customer outcomes will be negatively influenced (Mersland and Strøm, 2010). Generally, MFIs need more knowledge of how they can operate successfully, ethically and efficiently in increasingly competitive markets.

In addition to the six growth markets mentioned in this article there may be other markets driving continued microfinance growth. In particular agricultural lending should be watched. It is no doubt that there is an enormous demand for loans for agricultural purposes. Since the 1950s governments and international donors have searched for sustainable models to channel credit to poor farmers. So far it has been difficult to identify scalable and sustainable models without continued need for outside financial support. Innovation may bring along sustainable models, and if this happens the market for agricultural lending will definitely be among the future microfinance growth markets.

Researchers should look into how policy makers, regulators and international support organizations may encourage the future as outlined in this paper. At the same time it is important to keep in mind that public regulations may hamper the development described in this paper. That notwithstanding, customer protective regulations are important, especially for MFIs involved in deposit taking, insurance services and pension schemes. How to protect the money of poor customers without substantially increasing the costs of MFIs is among the most difficult questions for microfinance policy makers. This question should be on the forefront of the microfinance research agenda.

Will all MFIs go in the direction described in this paper? That is uncertain; several might even decide to end their involvement in microfinance. Some smaller socially focused MFIs will probably find market niches that may allow them to make more holistic efforts, including, for example, combining microfinance with other development efforts such as health services or education. Others will take the innovation route and come up with new products and services. Finally, several will most likely learn what BASIX India discovered several years ago: the poor do not demand financial services, they demand better livelihoods (www.thelivelihoodschool.org). My belief is that many NGO-MFIs, particularly those with access to donor support, will develop new initiatives to sustain and strengthen poor people's livelihoods, which may include both self-employment and access to formal jobs. A good area for future research would be to study how MFIs and other NGOs can improve the livelihoods of poor people.

What is certain is that MFIs will no longer have the microfinance market to themselves. Commercial and other banks have already entered the microfinance market in large numbers. At the same time, several MFIs have transformed into commercial banks. The boundaries between traditional banking and microfinance are blurring. Poor people are increasingly

considered as a market opportunity, and those interested in operating in this market will increasingly need to adopt traditional market strategies.

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